

The Tasks And Trials In PETE At The University Level in Japan

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Abstract

After the worldwide physical education crisis, so called PETE at university level is one of the focal point to promote quality Physical Education.

In this situation, in 1997, Education Personnel Training Council in Ministry of Education, Science and Culture (since 2001 Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology; MEXT) in Japan has informed the Council Report on strategy for improving teacher education system in the future. In 2008, the Course of Studies for elementary and junior high schools were introduced in 2008 and that of for senior high school in 2009. Also system for renewing educational personnel certificates is introduced formally from 2009. Based on this situation on PETE reform movement, tasks and trends in PETE at university level in Japan was shown in this article.

In Japanese PETE system, there is discrepancy between needed competency for physical education teachers and image of physical education teacher in general. Most important problem in this recognition would be poor knowledge on competencies requested for physical education teacher as profession. To overcome this discrepant, one need to discuss the better way to change employment system to profession.

At university level, even through simulated class based on reflection has introduced in some universities, content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge are usually taught separately. In this sense, one should consider again better way to enhance PCK at university level and to make tentative content and performance standard for them related with CPD. In this context, first step to improve PETE curriculum has just begun in JAPAN.

Key words: PETE, Reflection, Quality Physical Education, Content knowledge, Pedagogical knowledge, Pedagogical content knowledge, CPD

Introduction

After the worldwide physical education crisis [11, 7, 8] so called PETE (Physical Education Teacher Education) is one of the focal point to promote quality Physical Education. So AIESEP has set the Symposium on PETE and discussed the future direction in PETE worldwide [9]. Also Unesco [46] has shown the framework for international discussion on quality physical education and sport. In the Unesco's final report, promoting research on PETE is set as the one of the 6 tasks to be achieved in the future.

In Japan, in 1997, Education Personnel Training Council in Ministry of Education, Science and Culture (since 2001 Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology; MEXT) has informed the Council Report on strategy for improving teacher education system in the future. Also system for

renewing educational personnel certificates is introduced formally from 2009 in Japan.

At the same time, poor outcome in physical education classes, especially in elementary school was criticized in the discussion in the Central Council for Education [2]. Also Central Council for Education [3] has reported the future direction and expected outcomes in physical education. After these reports, in the ad hoc committee for revising the Course of Study, future direction and contents for the Course of Studies for Physical Education in each school levels were discussed. As the result, in 2008, the Course of Studies for elementary and junior high schools have informed [16, 17] and that of for senior high school in 2009 [18]. In these revisions, total number of physical education class has increased again from 90 hours per year to 105 hours per year in junior high school. In this sense, physical education teachers should be aware of their accountability to achieve goals

in the Course of Study much more. PETE at university level and also in service level should be key factor in this context.

On the other hand, in USA, NASPE [25, 26, 27] has published 1st edition of National Standards for Beginning Physical Education Teachers in 1995, it's 2nd edition in 2003 and it's 3rd edition in 2009. Through this process, requested competencies for beginning teachers have changed a little bit, but most important things in this process would be the fact that people in this research filed are always trying to find out better way to be accountable to the society.

For example, as the background of such publication, one recognize scientific research outcomes in sport pedagogy such as Graham [4, 5, 6], Metzler [15], Mosston [19, 20, 21, 22, 24], Rink, [29], Siedentop [33, 34, 35, 36, 37], and Silvermann [39, 40] and so on.

These research have shown teaching skills, instructional strategies and pedagogical models in physical education which should be acquired in the process of continual professional development (CPD) to implement effective physical education. On the other hands, research on teacher cognition and subjective theory has shown the importance of knowledge, value orientation and cooperation in teachers in professional community [10; 45; 47]. So such skills and knowledge are reflected in PETE program.

In this context, after about 2000, in Japan also, simulated classes based on reflection was rapidly introduced in PETE program at university level.

Aim

Based on such situation on PETE, background and trends in research on PETE in Japanese context would be shown in this article.

Materials and methods

To achieve this aim, following 2 documents were mainly analyzed based on recent research outcome in sport pedagogy.

1) document on PETE from MEXT after 1997.

2) document related with PETE in sport pedagogy.

Result and discussion

Request on Teacher Education at under graduate level from MEXT and required credits for Physical Education Teacher Certificates

Education Personnel Training Council [1] has shown expected competencies for teachers and divided them into two categories as shown in Tab.1.

Tab. 1 Expected competencies for teachers (Education Personel Training Council, 1997) [1]

Competencies requested to teachers at any time	Firm sense of mission as educator. Deep understanding about human growth and development. Educational affection to infant, pupils and student. Specific knowledge about subject content. Rich culture. Competency in teaching based on such components.
Competencies specially requested to teachers in the future	Competencies to behave with global aspects
	Competencies requested to be member of instable society
	Competencies requested from professional accountability

In the Japanese Education Personnel Certification Law, minimum requirement of credits for teaching certificates is regulated. Tab.2-4 show that of first-classes teaching certificates (undergraduate level) in junior and senior high school teachers. Student who would like to be physical education teachers should

take required credits in 4 categoirs; pedagogy, content knowledge, pedagogy and subject matter content and others (Tab.2). Lectures on pedagogy would be divided into general pedagogy and special pedagogy. Generally to say, in Japan, at the pre service level, acquisition of general competency as teachers would be

emphasized at university level training. In this context, students have only limited time to learn special knowledge in physical education pedagogy. For example, at Tsukuba university, student can take 6 credits for junior high schools certificates and 4 credits for senior high schools

teacher certificates in special pedagogy in physical education. Also 63 in 70 universities (61%) set between 6-8 credits lectures related with pedagogy in physical education [43].

Tab. 2 Minimum required credits for first-classes teaching certificates

	junior high schools	senior high schools
Lectures on pedagogy	31	26
Lectures on content knowledge	20	20
Lectures on pedagogy and subject matter content	8	16
Other lectures	10	10
Total Credits	69	72

Tab. 3 Minimum required credits on lectures on pedagogy for first-classes teaching certificates

	junior high schools	senior high schools
Lectures on meaning of teachers as profession	2	2
Lectures on basic pedagogy	6	6
Lectures on curriculum and teaching methods	12	6
Lectures on student guidance, educational counseling and career guidance	4	4
Seminar on integrated learning	2	2
Practice in schools	5	3
Total Credits	31	23

Tab. 4 Minimum required credits for first-classes teaching certificates on lectures on content knowledge in physical education

	junior high schools	senior high schools
practice	More than 1 credit	More than 1 credit
"Sport philosophy or Sport psychology or Sport administration or Sport sociology" and Training science(including teaching methods)	More than 1 credit	More than 1 credit
Physiology(including Exercise physiology)	More than 1 credit	More than 1 credit
Hygiene and Public Health	More than 1 credit	More than 1 credit
School Health(including infant health, mental health, security in school and First-aid)	More than 1 credit	More than 1 credit
Total Credits	20	20

Discrepancy between needed competencies for physical education teachers

In the revised Course of Study for Physical Education in junior high schools, development of competencies for life time sport is set as the goal of physical education class [16]. To achieve this goal, physical education teachers should develop and improve their competencies based on pedagogical content knowledge in this subject.

On the other hands, the Education Personnel Certification Law request pre service teachers to complete only at least 1 credit in sport practice. Also in related to the Course of Study, in some universities, pre-service teachers should complete Budo credit such as Judo and Kendo because Budo is taught in many junior high schools. But, this regulation is not enough to enhance content knowledge in physical education in junior and senior high schools. So at the examination for employment as in service teachers, most of prefectural administration set performance test in 4 sport disciplines in average. There is discrepant between requested competencies at universities and that of expected at educational board and schools.

On the other hand, image of physical education teacher is so diverse. One think physical education teachers as coach for after school sport club in schools or teachers responsible for educational guidance.

In this sense, one could find out discrepancy between needed competencies for physical education teachers and image of physical education teacher in general. Most important problem in this recognition would be poor knowledge on competencies requested for physical education teacher as profession. As other subject teachers, physical education teacher should develop special competencies requested in this subject area as profession.

Problem in pre service PETE curriculum and staffs awareness at universities

As mentioned above, student in pre service program in university should acquire knowledge and skills on pedagogy and content in this subject. But implementing quality and effective

teacher education program at university is not easy. There would be many reasons, but one could summarize reasons from following 5 points;

1) Attitude of staffs in university to PETE/ They should be responsible for teacher education, but there are surely some staffs in teacher education program who are so strongly oriented only to their own major science and have little enthusiasm about physical education teacher education program.

2) Weak connection of lecture content with realistic problems in physical education class.

3) Student's poor sport performance in physical education major.

4) Poor ability to teach health education.

5) Image of teachers characterized as consumer of knowledge [31].

Recently, teacher is recognized as active learner and also cooperative creator of knowledge in profession. But, the concrete curriculum based on this teacher image is not yet developed.

Based on Takahashi's report [43], only in 25 universities in 52 universities (45%), all lectures on pedagogy in physical education were taught by staffs who are members of Japan Society of Pedagogy for Physical Education. In contrary, 6 (11%) universities have no major staffs in Pedagogy for Physical Education. Also in 133 lectures in 188 lectures, procedure for lesson planning is taught, but knowledge in pedagogy for physical education isn't taught enough to make realistic lesson plan.

Some trials for improving present physical education teacher education curriculum status quo

As already reported in other countries [14], one can find out also easily some trial to change PETE program at university level in Japan.

For example, 81% of all lectures in 63 universities are taught in lecture style. On the other hands, in 30% in 63 universities which have PETE program, simulated class is introduce in lectures in pedagogy in physical education. Also 13% in those 63 universities, simulated class is given as the independent lecture [43].

In this trial to improve PETE program at university level, one can recognize performance orientation and also reflection orientation in it. Like in Australia [14], New Zealand and USA [45, 12] et al., after about 2000, in Japan also, some PETE staffs have begun to introduce reflection based simulated classes in PETE program.

For example, in simulated classes, teacher behavior was taken in video and analyzed through systematic observation. Teachers and students can understand some tendency in their teacher behavior easily based on such analyzed data. These data are also used to promote reflection on their performance and also student performance and procedure in simulated classes in peer group or by oneself. With such reflection, one can improve their performance and also deepen their reflection on simulated physical education classes [30].

Basic concepts in such PETE program are constituted with following 2 points;

1) Let pre service teachers to move from the position to be taught to the position to teach. With enhancing teaching experience, they can be aware of need of learning skills. It makes them easier to acquire basic teaching skills, pedagogical models in physical education and improve their image on quality physical education

2) Let pre service teachers experience collaboration in professional community. In cooperating with peers to make lesson plan, observe teaching behavior using systematic observation system, analyze outcomes and discuss the better lesson plan would give them indispensable experience in tentative professional community. Indeed, only in 3 days intensive program, pre service student at university level could develop their teaching skills like management skills and interaction skills.

On the other hand, it is hard to enhance content knowledge and believes on teaching in physical education in short time course without direct teaching experience for K - 12 pupils. To enhance their PCK, long term curriculum development would be requested for promoting CPD.

These trials are also supported by publication of academic research outcomes in journals and so on. Through this support,

information on effective physical education and teaching skills in physical education, and procedure to promote effective reflection in undergraduate level are shared with teachers in this profession.

For example, books based on academic research outcomes for pre service teachers [41, 42, 44] are published and used at university level to improve competencies in teaching physical education. Not only introducing simulated PE class and lesson analysis through systematic observation system, but also using simple questionnaire to learners based on enhancing teaching experience, one could activate more effective reflection on physical education lesson and also improve their ability to reflect in action.

Conclusion: some remarks in the future direction in PETE curriculum development in JAPAN

To overcome the discrepant, one need to discuss the better way to change employment system to profession. Also to achieve quality physical education in schools based on the revised Course of Studies in Japan, quality physical education curriculum development in professional community, PETE curriculum and also CPD are indispensable. On the other hand, to evaluate effectiveness of such programs, we need appropriate assessment tools for these tasks and also criteria to evaluate it. Content standard and performance standard for expected competencies at pre service level should be shown based on academic evidence.

In this context, some research have suggested following points to make PETE curriculum more effective;

1) Enhance experience to know schools, learners and profession.

2) Recognize importance of reflection in professional community.

It would be very hard to make pre service teachers in PETE curriculum at university level to acquire specific content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge enough to teach in school setting because of time limitation, teacher's believe and environment conditions so on.

In addition, as mentioned above, at university level, content knowledge and

pedagogical knowledge are taught separately. Even though simulated class is introduced into PETE curriculum, in this system, it would be hard to combine and enhance both knowledge needed for teaching. One expects it in 3 weeks school practice, but expected outcome of it depends on usually on mentors ability and their strategies [45].

In this sense, one should consider again better way to enhance PCK at university level. Making tentative content and performance standard for them related in considering with CPD would be one of such idea. To make reliable proposal on this task, we need much more scientific evidence in cooperation with schools, administrations and universities. To change teacher image would be the first step.

Teachers are not passive learners to learn knowledge for practice, they are also active learners and researchers to produce knowledge of practice. They enhance also their knowledge in practice through reflection [32].

Also content and curriculum for PETE at university level should be reconstructed based on research evidence [43]. In the process for this reconstruction, one should define standard for beginning PE teachers such as NASPE's proposal [25, 26 27] and assess outcomes in PETE curriculum. Off course, as explained above, one can find out some trials to change present status quo. In this sense, first step to change PETE curriculum has just began in JAPAN.

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